

AI-Driven Human Wi-Fi Sensing with Hierarchical Architecture and Breathing Detection

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Abstract—This paper presents an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered Wi-Fi channel state information human sensing system via breathing detection as a wellness feature through a three-layer hierarchical architecture. The system combines a two-stage pipeline (activity detection pre-filtering followed by breathing detection) with temporal user state tracking and semantic classification. Based on three features (Breathing-to-Noise Ratio, Subcarrier Agreement, and Nonlinearity), our activity detection model achieves 88.5% F1-score on test data, and the breathing detection model 96.47% F1-score. Operating at 20 Hz sampling rate with 8 sec processing windows, the system enables intelligent wellness monitoring while maintaining cross-dataset robustness. Extensive validation across independent datasets demonstrates consistent high accuracy, making this approach suitable for realistic deployment in presence-aware computing, wellness monitoring, and human-computer interaction applications.

Index Terms—AI human sensing, Wi-Fi sensing, breathing detection, wellness monitoring, presence detection, machine learning, logistic regression, human-computer interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Contactless human sensing using Wi-Fi Channel State Information (CSI) has emerged as a promising technology for presence detection and vital sign monitoring [1]–[5]. Traditional Wi-Fi sensing relies on passive monitoring between separate transmitters (Tx) and receivers (Rx). We instead introduce an innovative active sensing architecture where both Tx and Rx are co-located within a single device (e.g., a laptop), operating without requiring a separate Wi-Fi access point. This monostatic configuration enables radar-like human sensing optimized for human-laptop interaction, where the laptop becomes an intelligent sensor monitoring surrounding users’ presence and vital signs.

Wi-Fi CSI-based systems offer privacy-preserving, non-intrusive monitoring by analyzing how human presence affects wireless signal propagation. However, distinguishing subtle breathing patterns from larger movements and environmental interference remains challenging, mostly at varying distances from sensing devices. Proximity-dependent signal characteristics create a fundamental problem: breathing detection near the sensor (1-2 m) benefits from strong reflections, while activity detection at greater distances (3-5 m) requires different feature representations. Traditional single-stage classifiers fail to address this dual-detection requirement, resulting in a high number of false positives or missed detections.

To address the aforementioned issues, we present a novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) human sensing system with a three-

layer hierarchical architecture achieving high accuracy through explicit multi-scale detection modeling. Our two-stage pipeline consists of: (1) an activity detection classifier identifying time windows containing human presence using motion-sensitive features, followed by (2) a breathing detection classifier analyzing only active windows using breathing-specific features. This staged approach allows each model to specialize in its detection regime. Key contributions of this paper include:

- Active sensing architecture with co-located Tx/Rx operating without Wi-Fi access points for human-laptop interaction
- Three-layer hierarchical architecture: two-stage ML detection, temporal state tracking (15 sec buffer, 70% threshold), and semantic classification (six categories)
- Three unique features (BNR, FpXAgr, c3) discriminating breathing from motion artifacts
- Signal processing pipeline: Long Training Field (LTF) alignment with 2x upsampling, phase correction, and Savitzky-Golay smoothing [6].

Wi-Fi-based human sensing has evolved significantly, with systems like WiSee [7] and WiTrack [8] demonstrating gesture recognition using passive bistatic configurations. Vital-Radio [2] achieved breathing and heart rate monitoring using wireless signals reflected off the human body. However, these passive approaches require existing Wi-Fi infrastructure and struggle with distinguishing breathing from periodic movements or addressing proximity-dependent detection.

Our active sensing architecture, which is an extension of the work done in [9], eliminates the need for separate Wi-Fi access points through co-located Tx-Rx configuration, enabling dedicated human-laptop interaction monitoring. The proposed monostatic design provides superior control over signal acquisition, enabling our robust two-stage detection pipeline. We leverage tsfresh-based feature extraction, particularly the c3 statistic for detecting non-stationary physiological signals [10]. Our innovation exploits multipath propagation characteristics in indoor environments to achieve robust motion detection and breathing pattern discrimination through carefully engineered features. Our three-layer architecture integrates multi-scale detection, temporal state tracking, and semantic classification for real-time processing, and has been partially developed under the work of the EU-funded research projects 6G-SENSES [11] and MultiX [12].

Fig. 1. Active sensing system monitoring the user's movements.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the three-layer system architecture and its key components; Section III details signal processing techniques and feature extraction methods; Section IV presents the training workflow and optimization process; Section V reports experimental results and performance evaluation, and finally Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our system implements a three-layer hierarchical architecture that progressively refines raw CSI measurements into high-level semantic classifications. This design separates concerns between signal-level detection (Layer 1), temporal context integration (Layer 2), and semantic interpretation (Layer 3). Figure 1 shows the monostatic active sensing configuration, where the laptop serves as both Tx and Rx, and Figure 2 the complete three-layer hierarchical architecture.

A. Layer 1: Two-Stage ML Detection

The key innovation of our system is the two-stage pipeline that addresses the core challenge of multi-scale detection:

Stage 1: Activity Detection

The activity detector performs binary classification (ACTIVITY vs NO_ACTIVITY) to identify 8 sec windows containing any form of human presence or movement. This stage uses the motion-sensitive features derived from tsfresh [10] statistical descriptors computed on 10 Hz motion scores (one score per 100 ms, derived from two consecutive 20 Hz CSI samples). The 10 Hz sampling rate is optimal for capturing human motion (walking at 1-2 Hz, approaching at 0.5-1 Hz, arm movements at 1-3 Hz) per Nyquist theorem while minimizing autocorrelation computation cost.

Stage 2: Breathing Detection

The breathing classifier operates only on windows labeled as ACTIVITY by Stage 1, performing binary classification (BREATHING vs OTHER) using three unique features:

- Breathing-to-Noise Ratio (BNR): Energy concentration in breathing frequency band
- Subcarrier Agreement (FpXAgr): Spatial consistency of breathing pattern across subcarriers
- Nonlinearity (c3): Autocovariance-based measure of signal regularity.

Fig. 2. Three-layer hierarchical architecture.

The two-stage design prevents far-field activity signals from being misclassified as breathing (reducing false positives) while maintaining sensitivity to near-field breathing patterns (preserving recall).

B. Layer 2: User State Tracking

Layer 2 integrates temporal context by tracking user state over a 15 sec baseline buffer. The system applies a 70% threshold to determine stable state classifications:

- USER_NEAR_PC: Breathing detected in $\geq 70\%$ of the windows in buffer
- USER_AWAY_FROM_PC: No breathing detected in $\geq 70\%$ of the windows
- UNKNOWN: Transitional state when the threshold is not met.

This temporal smoothing eliminates spurious transitions caused by brief signal fluctuations while maintaining responsiveness to genuine state changes (a typical transition detection happens within 3-5 sec).

C. Layer 3: Semantic Classification

Layer 3 maps low-level detector outputs and state transitions to six human-interpretable semantic classes:

- APPROACH: Transition from AWAY \rightarrow NEAR
- WALK_AWAY: Transition from NEAR \rightarrow AWAY
- RESPIRATION_DETECTED: Stable NEAR state
- NO_RESPIRATION: Stable AWAY state
- SIGNIFICANT_MOTION: Activity without breathing signature
- OTHER: Ambiguous or transitional states.

This semantic layer enables application-level decision making without requiring retraining of underlying models. Rule-based classification logic maps detector outputs and state transitions to semantic categories based on temporal patterns and confidence levels.

III. SIGNAL PROCESSING AND FEATURE EXTRACTION

A. Measurement Setup

Wi-Fi Sensing Platform: This work employs a Lenovo ThinkPad L14 Gen 5 equipped with Intel Core Ultra 7 155U processor (14-inch, 32 GB RAM) and Intel Wi-Fi 6E chipset with CSI extraction capability operating in the 802.11ax mode. By utilizing active sensing with concurrent transmission and reception on two antennas, the system achieves radar-like operation, in contrast to conventional passive Wi-Fi sensing.

Operating Parameters: The system is configured with the following parameters:

- Frequency Band: 6 GHz (Wi-Fi 6E)
- Channel Bandwidth: 20 MHz
- Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) Subcarriers: 52 total subcarriers
- Target Sampling Rate: 20 Hz.

B. CSI Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

The system processes CSI data from the Lenovo ThinkPad L14 Gen 5 configured with Intel Wi-Fi chipset operating in 20 MHz bandwidth mode with 52 OFDM subcarriers at 20 Hz sampling rate. Raw CSI measurements provide complex-valued channel estimates $H[k, t]$ for subcarrier k at time t , capturing both amplitude and phase information of wireless channel propagation. For motion-sensitive features used in activity detection, motion scores are computed at 10 Hz (derived from every 2 CSI samples), which optimally captures human motion frequencies (typically below 5 Hz) while reducing computational overhead by 50% compared to full-rate processing. The signal processing pipeline has three critical stages:

- LTF Alignment: LTF symbols are aligned using 2x up-sampling to correct for timing synchronization errors that cause phase rotation artifacts
- Phase Correction: A phase unwrapping algorithm removes π -radian phase jumps that occur due to carrier frequency offset in 20 MHz bandwidth mode
- Savitzky-Golay Smoothing: The Savitzky-Golay filtering provides noise reduction while preserving signal features.

C. Feature Extraction

1) *Breathing-to-Noise Ratio:* BNR quantifies the concentration of signal energy within the breathing frequency band relative to total signal energy. For each subcarrier k , we compute the power spectral density $P_k(f)$ using Welch's method [13], then calculate:

$$BNR_k = \frac{\int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} P_k(f) df}{\int_0^{f_s/2} P_k(f) df} \quad (1)$$

where $f_{min} = 0.16$ Hz and $f_{max} = 0.62$ Hz define the breathing band, and $f_s = 20$ Hz is the sampling rate. The final BNR feature is the mean across the top one-third of subcarriers ranked by individual BNR values, focusing on subcarriers with the strongest breathing signatures.

Higher BNR values (> 0.4) indicate dominant breathing patterns, while lower values (< 0.2) suggest noise-dominated signals or non-breathing movement.

2) *Subcarrier Agreement:* FpXAgr measures the spatial consistency of breathing patterns across multiple subcarriers. Due to multipath propagation, breathing-induced CSI variations should exhibit coherent frequency peaks across subcarriers, while random noise or environmental interference show incoherent patterns.

For each subcarrier in the top one-third by BNR weighting, we identify the frequency of the first spectral peak $f_{peak,k}$. FpXAgr is computed as:

$$FpXAgr = \frac{N_{agree}}{N_{total}} \quad (2)$$

where N_{agree} is the count of subcarriers whose first peak frequency falls within ± 0.05 Hz of the median peak frequency, and N_{total} is the total number of analyzed subcarriers.

High FpXAgr values (> 0.7) indicate spatially coherent breathing patterns, while low values (< 0.3) suggest uncorrelated noise or movement artifacts.

3) *Nonlinearity:* The c3 statistic captures the non-Gaussian, nonlinear characteristics of breathing signals using autocovariance analysis. For a time series $x[n]$, c3 is computed as:

$$c3 = \frac{1}{N - 2\tau} \sum_{n=1}^{N-2\tau} x[n] \cdot x[n + \tau] \cdot x[n + 2\tau] \quad (3)$$

where $\tau = 1$ is the lag parameter and N is the window length (160 samples for 8 sec windows at 20 Hz).

Breathing signals exhibit characteristic nonlinear autocorrelation due to periodic chest wall movement with physiological constraints (inhalation/exhalation asymmetry), producing elevated c3 values compared to linear random processes or simple harmonic motion. We implement c3 using the tsfresh library with default parameters [10].

D. Window-Based Processing

All features are computed over 8 sec sliding windows. This window length balances:

- Sufficient duration to capture 2-3 breathing cycles (for 15-25 breaths/min rates)
- Adequate frequency resolution (0.125 Hz bins) for breathing band analysis
- Real-time processing latency (< 500 ms per window)
- Temporal responsiveness to state transitions (4 sec update rate).

Each 8 sec window yields a 3-dimensional feature vector [BNR, FpXAgr, c3] for breathing detection (computed from 160 CSI samples at 20 Hz) and a 5-dimensional vector for activity detection (computed from 80 motion scores at 10 Hz). The dual-rate sampling strategy optimizes computational efficiency while maintaining detection accuracy for both breathing (requiring 20 Hz for 0.16-0.62 Hz band analysis) and motion (adequately captured at 10 Hz for human activity below 5 Hz).

IV. WORKFLOW DESCRIPTION

The complete workflow follows a five-step pipeline from raw data collection to model deployment:

A. Training Data Collection and Labeling

1) *Raw CSI Data Collection*: It is performed using automated data collection utility with controlled experimental protocols. For each class, 5-10 recording sessions of 240 sec duration is collected to ensure sufficient training data diversity:

Breathing Class Collection:

- Subject positioned 30-50 cm from laptop in stationary seated position
- Natural breathing at rest without deliberate breath control
- Multiple sessions across different times of day and environmental conditions
- Data saved with `breathing` label tag for subsequent processing.

Other Class Collection:

- Empty room scenarios only (no human presence)
- Data saved with `other` label tag for subsequent processing.

The "Other" class for training consists exclusively of empty room data without human presence. Activities such as approach, walk-away, and other background motions are not included in the training dataset; instead, these scenarios are classified post-inference by Layer 3 semantic classification (Section II-C) based on detector outputs and temporal state transitions.

Each recording session generates timestamped CSI data files containing corrected complex-valued channel estimates, LTF reference signals, and metadata for downstream processing.

2) *Batch Labeling for Activity Detection Training*: It processes collected sessions using pattern-based label assignment:

ACTIVITY Label Assignment: All sessions matching pattern `session_*_Breathing*` are automatically labeled as `ACTIVITY` class, identifying windows containing human presence (breathing constitutes detectable activity).

NO_ACTIVITY Label Assignment: All sessions matching pattern `session_*_Other*` are automatically labeled as `NO_ACTIVITY` class, identifying windows with absent or distant human presence.

Batch labeling ensures consistent label assignment across large datasets and eliminates manual annotation errors for Stage 1 (activity detection) training.

B. Model Architecture and Training

Both activity detection and breathing detection models use identical pipeline architectures implementing a three-stage transformation:

$$\text{Raw Features} \xrightarrow{\text{SimpleImputer}} \xrightarrow{\text{StandardScaler}} \xrightarrow{\text{LogisticRegression}} \text{Prediction} \quad (4)$$

SimpleImputer: Handles missing values (rare, < 2% of features) using a median strategy. Missing values occur when

spectral analysis fails due to insufficient signal quality during feature extraction.

StandardScaler: Is critical for combining features with different value ranges (e.g., $\text{BNR} \in [0, 1]$ vs $\text{c3} \in [-10, 10]$) and makes use of the Z-score normalization, which ensures equal feature contribution during optimization.

LogisticRegression: Implements a L2-regularized linear classifier with hyperparameters optimized via grid search:

- Regularization strength $C \in \{0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100\}$
- Solver: `lbfgs` (limited-memory BFGS) for activity detection; `liblinear` for breathing detection
- Max iterations: 1000 (ensures convergence)
- Class weight: balanced (compensates for slight class imbalance).

Training Execution: The activity detection model is trained on batch-labeled motion score features, the breathing detection model on breathing-specific features (BNR, `FpXAgr`, `c3`) extracted from recording sessions. Both models utilize automated training pipelines with comprehensive logging and checkpoint management.

To rigorously validate our model selection for real-time edge deployment on notebooks, we conducted a comprehensive comparison of three approaches on the breathing detection task (9,944 test samples): (1) logistic regression (LR) (original), (2) LR with polynomial features (degree-2, interaction-only), and (3) Support Vector Machine (SVM) with Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. Table I presents a comparison across performance, computational efficiency, and edge deployment suitability. The LR (original) was selected as our deployment model based on the following critical advantages:

- **Optimal performance-efficiency trade-off**: F1-score of 96.47% with only 0.70% degradation compared to SVM (97.18%), while achieving $23\times$ faster inference (0.44 ms vs 10 ms) and $138\times$ smaller model size (1.58 KB vs 219 KB)
- **Memory footprint**: 1.58 KB model size enables deployment on resource-constrained edge devices (fits in CPU L1/L2 cache)
- **Polynomial features ineffective**: Adding degree-2 polynomial features (expanding 3 features to 6) degraded F1-score by 0.18% (96.29% vs 96.47%), indicating the original 3 features (BNR, `FpXAgr`, `c3`) already capture optimal decision boundaries
- **SVM impractical for edge deployment**: While SVM achieves the highest accuracy (97.18% F1), the 10 ms inference time violates real-time constraints and 219 KB model size exceeds typical edge device memory budgets (target: < 10 KB for CPU cache residence).
- **Real-time edge deployment**: Original LR provides the optimal performance-efficiency trade-off for notebook edge deployment: (a) inference time of 0.44 ms enables seamless integration with 20 Hz CSI sampling pipeline, (b) 1.58 KB model fits entirely in CPU L1/L2 cache (32-256 KB typical), eliminating memory access latency, and (c) 96.47% F1-score meets wellness monitoring accuracy

TABLE I
MODEL COMPARISON: PERFORMANCE, EFFICIENCY, AND EDGE DEPLOYMENT SUITABILITY

Model	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	AUC-ROC	Inference (ms)	Size (KB)	Edge Deployable
LR (Original)	0.9647	0.9716	0.9579	0.9945	0.440	1.58	✓
LR + Polynomial	0.9629	0.9748	0.9513	0.9949	0.523	1.91	✓
SVM (RBF)	0.9718	0.9843	0.9595	0.9832	10.000	219.00	×
<i>Efficiency gains vs SVM (RBF):</i>							
LR (Original)	23× faster inference, 138× smaller model size						
LR + Polynomial	19× faster inference, 115× smaller model size						

requirements. The 23× speedup and 138× size reduction vs SVM justify accepting 0.70% lower F1-score for practical real-world deployment.

Accordingly, LR (original) is assessed according to the following analysis.

C. Cross-Validation and Hyperparameter Optimization

We employ a 10-fold stratified cross-validation with comprehensive grid search:

- 1) Partition training data into 10 stratified folds (maintaining class distribution)
- 2) For each hyperparameter configuration:
 - Train on 9 folds, validate on 1 fold (repeat 10 times)
 - Compute mean validation F1-score across all folds
- 3) Select configuration with the highest mean validation F1-score
- 4) Retrain on full training set using optimal hyperparameters
- 5) Evaluate on held-out test set (never seen during training/validation).

This approach provides robust performance estimates and prevents overfitting to specific data partitions. The held-out test set ensures unbiased assessment of real-world generalization.

D. Model Persistence and Deployment

Trained models are serialized using the standard Python pickle format with accompanying JSON metadata containing:

- Complete pipeline (imputer, scaler, and classifier)
- Training history (F1, precision, recall, and Area Under the Curve (AUC) metrics)
- Hyperparameter configurations (optimal settings from grid search)
- Feature definitions (names and ordering for reproducibility)

This standardized format enables seamless integration with the real-time processing system.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND EVALUATION

A. Performance Metrics

We evaluate model performance using four standard metrics computed on the held-out test set. The metrics are derived from the confusion matrix, including True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN). Based on these confusion matrix elements, we can compute the following parameters:

- **Precision (P):** $P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ - proportion of positive predictions that are correct
- **Recall (R):** $R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ - proportion of actual positives correctly identified
- **F1-Score:** $F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{P \cdot R}{P+R}$ - harmonic mean of precision and recall
- **AUC-ROC:** Area under Rx operating characteristic curve - overall discrimination capability

All metrics are computed using sklearn.metrics with default thresholds (0.5 probability cutoff).

B. Activity Detection Model Results

Table II summarizes the activity detection model performance obtained across training, validation, and test sets.

TABLE II
ACTIVITY DETECTION MODEL PERFORMANCE

Dataset	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	AUC-ROC
Training (218)	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Validation (31)	1.0000	0.9375	0.9677	0.9583
Test (63)	0.9000	0.8710	0.8852	0.9637

The activity detection model achieves 90.0% precision and 87.1% recall on the test set, with an F1-score of 88.5%. This provides reliable activity detection while maintaining low false alarm rates, critical for the two-stage pipeline.

The model demonstrates stable performance across training (100% F1), validation (96.8% F1), and test (88.5% F1) sets, with the test performance remaining above practical deployment thresholds. Herein, we consider the optimal hyperparameters $C = 10$ and L1 penalty, making use of the liblinear solver.

C. Breathing Detection Model Results

The breathing detection model presented in Table III achieves strong performance on the test set: 97.16 precision, 95.79 recall, 96.47 F1-score, and 99.45 AUC-ROC.

TABLE III
BREATHING DETECTION MODEL PERFORMANCE

Dataset	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	AUC-ROC
Training (34784)	0.9735	0.9504	0.9618	0.9944
Validation (4970)	0.9749	0.9549	0.9648	0.9949
Test (9944)	0.9716	0.9579	0.9647	0.9945

Fig. 3. Confusion matrices on test data (Left: Activity detection model; Right: Breathing detection model.)

The obtained results demonstrate that when operating on pre-filtered ACTIVITY windows (Stage 1 output), the breathing-specific features (BNR, FpXAgr, c3) provide robust discrimination. With consistent performance across training (96.18 F1), validation (96.48 F1), and test (96.47 F1) sets, the model shows excellent generalization on 9,944 test samples, exceeding the 90 F1-score target. Herein, we consider the optimal hyperparameters $C = 0.1$ and L1 penalty, making use of the liblinear solver.

D. Confusion Matrix Analysis

Figure 3 shows confusion matrices for both models on test data.

The activity detection confusion matrix reveals:

- 3 false positives (NO_ACTIVITY windows misclassified as ACTIVITY)
- 4 false negatives out of 31 true ACTIVITY windows (12.9% miss rate)
- Missed detections occur primarily for distant users (4-5 meters) performing subtle movements
- Overall accuracy: 88.9% on 63 test samples.

The breathing detection confusion matrix shows strong classification performance:

- 139 false positives (OTHER windows misclassified as BREATHING, 2.79% of OTHER class)
- 209 false negatives (BREATHING windows misclassified as OTHER, 4.21% of BREATHING class)
- 4,839 true negatives (correctly classified OTHER windows)
- 4,757 true positives (correctly classified BREATHING windows)
- Overall accuracy: 96.47% on 9,944 test samples.

E. Cross-Validation Stability

10-fold cross-validation results demonstrate stable performance across data partitions:

Activity Detection: Best CV F1 = 0.931, with mean train score 0.804 and mean test score 0.754, indicating the model learns meaningful patterns while avoiding overfitting.

Breathing: Best CV F1 = 0.963, with mean train score 0.949 and mean test score 0.949, showing excellent stability and generalization.

Consistent performance between training and test folds confirms that models generalize well and are not overfitted to specific training subsets.

VI. CONCLUSION

We present an AI-driven human Wi-Fi sensing system with a three-layer hierarchical architecture and breathing detection. The two-stage pipeline achieves robust activity detection (88.5% F1-score) and breathing detection (96.47% F1-score). The proposed tree unique features (BNR, FpXAgr, c3) provide robust discrimination between breathing and motion artifacts, while a comprehensive signal processing pipeline ensures high-quality CSI inputs.

Temporal state tracking (15 sec buffer, 70% threshold) eliminates spurious transitions, and semantic classification enables application-level interpretation for wellness monitoring, presence-aware computing, and contactless health tracking.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Origin Wireless, Inc., "AI-Enabled WiFi Sensing: Creating an Intelligent, Connected Ecosystem," White Paper, May 2025.
- [2] F. Adib, H. Mao, Z. Kabelac, D. Katabi, and R. C. Miller, "Smart Homes that Monitor Breathing and Heart Rate," in Proc. ACM CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 2015, pp. 837–846.
- [3] V. Frascolla, D. Cavalcanti, R. Shah, "Wi-Fi Evolution: The Path Towards Wi-Fi 7 and its impact on IIoT", Journal of Mobile Multimedia, vol. 19, no. 01, p. 263–276, Sep. 2022.
- [4] J. Sanson, R. Shah, M. Pinaroc, and V. Frascolla, "Extracting Range-Doppler Information of Moving Targets from Wi-Fi Channel State Information," Dec. 2025, proceedings of the 2025 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM). [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.02799>.
- [5] J. Sanson, R. Shah, V. Frascolla "Human Presence Detection via Wi-Fi Range-Filtered Doppler Spectrum on Commodity Laptops", to appear in Proc of the 3rd International Workshop on Pervasive Wireless Sensing and Edge Computing (WiSense), 2026.
- [6] M. Niedzwiecki et al., "Application of regularized Savitzky-Golay filters to identification of time-varying systems," Automatica, vol 133, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2021.10986>.
- [7] Q. Pu et al., "Whole-home Gesture Recognition Using Wireless Signals," in Proc. ACM MobiCom, 2013, pp. 27–38.
- [8] F. Adib and D. Katabi, "See Through Walls with Wi-Fi!" in Proc. ACM SIGCOMM, 2013, pp. 75–86.
- [9] Y. Zhu, R. Shah, V. Frascolla, "OFDM-Based mmWave Wi-Fi ISAC System Implementation for Monostatic Human Sensing," to appear in Proc. of the 20th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), 2026.
- [10] M. Christ, N. Braun, J. Neuffer, and A. W. Kempa-Liehr, "Time Series Feature Extraction on basis of Scalable Hypothesis tests (tsfresh – A Python package)," Neurocomputing, vol. 307, pp. 72–77, 2018.
- [11] J. Gutiérrez et al., "Seamless integration of efficient 6G wireless technologies for communication and sensing enabling ecosystems," in Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations. AIAI 2024 IFIP WG 12.5 International Workshops, I. Maglogiannis et al., Eds. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 190–201.
- [12] X. Li et al., "MultiX: Advancing 6G-RAN Through Multi-Technology, Multi-Sensor Fusion, Multi-Band and Multi-Static Perception," IEEE Wireless Communications, pp. 1–8, 2025.
- [13] D. S. Borisov and A. V. Blagov, "Comparison of Welch and Lomb-Scargle Methods for Constructing a Periodogram for Uniform Time Series of Locomotor Activity," 2024 X International Conference on Information Technology and Nanotechnology (ITNT), Samara, Russian Federation, 2024, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ITNT60778.2024.10582330.